

TABLE-1 CHARACTERISATION DATA OF DICYANDIAMIDINE *p*-TOLUENESULPHONATE (C₉H₁₄N₄O₆S) AND *p*-TOLUENESULPHONYLDICYANDIAMIDE (C₉H₁₀N₄O₅S)

Compound	M.P. (°C)	Carbon (%)	Hydrogen (%)	Nitrogen (%)	Sulphur (%)
C ₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆ S					
Method-1**	234.5	—	—	20.0(20.4)*	11.9(11.7)
Method-2	235.0	—	—	20.4(20.4)	11.5(11.7)
Method-3	235.0	40.0(39.4)	5.4(5.1)	20.3(20.4)	11.8(11.7)
C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₅ S	191.0	45.1(45.4)	4.5(4.2)	23.7(23.5)	13.8(13.5)

*Calculated values are in parentheses.

**Sen and Gupta's analyses are : M.P. (235°) ; % Nitrogen 23.4(23.5)

(8.4 g) was suspended in acetone (120 ml) and sodium hydroxide (10 g in 20 ml water) was added. The mixture was cooled to 18° and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (19.1 g) was added gradually with stirring, while the temperature was maintained at 18°. After the reaction mixture was stirred for four hours it was allowed to stand overnight. The solution was diluted with water (100 ml) and neutralised with acetic acid. *p*-Toluenesulphonyldicyandiamide separated as white crystals. These were recrystallised from methanol and dried in air.

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1. R. L. DUTTA and A. M. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1000, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, 40, 417.
2. A. B. SEN and S. K. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 578.
3. A. D. CROSS, *Practical Infrared Spectroscopy*, Butterworths Publication Ltd., 1960, p.64.
4. F. J. WELCHER, *Organic Analytical Reagents*. Vol. 1, D. VAN Nostrand Co. Inc., New York, 1947, p.417.
5. P. S. WINNEK, G. W. ANDERSON, H. W. MARSON, H. E. FAITH and R. O. ROBLIN, Jr. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1682.

Stereochemical Studies on Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with *p*-Dimethyl Amino-9-anthracyl Glyoxal Anil

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NEW complexes of Co(II) and Ni(II) with *p*-dimethyl amino 9-anthracyl glyoxalanil (DIMAGA) of the type [M(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)₂(Cl)₂] [where M=Co(II), Ni(II)] have been prepared and characterised on the basis of various physicochemical studies. Magnetic

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moment and electronic-spectral studies of the complexes reveal the octahedral stereochemistry. The i. r. data indicate (M-O), (M-N) and (M-Cl) stretching frequencies in the range 575-560, 520-500 and 340-320 cm⁻¹ respectively.

Recently, in connection with our interest in the stereochemical studies on transition metal complexes with DIMAGA^{1,2}, we here report the synthesis of Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes with DIMAGA and their characterization by chemical-analysis, molecular conductance, magnetic moment (at 305°K using Guoy's method), electronic spectra (indioxane) and infra-red studies.

Preparation and Isolation of Complexes : Dichlorobis-(DIMAGA) Cobalt(II)/Nickel(II) : The acetonetic solution of NiCl₂.6H₂O or CoCl₂.6H₂O (2.37 g., 10 m. mole) was mixed with (7.04 g., 20 m. mole) of the ligand DIMAGA in the same solvent and dark-grey (Co-complex) and buff-green (Ni-complex) precipitates obtained were digested, cooled, filtered and washed with small amounts of ethanol, acetonitrile and acetone. The products were dried at 80°-90° for about 30 minutes. The molar conductance of the complexes in 10⁻³ M DMF solution [$\lambda_m = 20.89$ and 11.5 mhos for Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes respectively] suggest their non-electrolytic nature.

Chemicals of 'AnalaR' grade are used throughout. Elemental analysis was made for both the complexes and satisfactory agreement was obtained between found and calculated values revealing metal to ligand stoichiometric ratio as 1 : 2. The electronic spectra were recorded in dioxane using Hilger UviA-peck spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements and i. r. spectra of the complexes were undertaken as described earlier.¹

The observed magnetic moment in Co(II) complex (4.60 B. M.) is slightly lower to the spin only value, which indicates low spin octahedral stereochemistry with incomplete quenching of the orbital contribution to the magnetic moment.³ The observed magnetic moment in Ni(II) complex (2.98 B.M.) also suggests octahedral symmetry. The slight increase in magnetic moment value from that of the spin only value may be due to some sort of mixing of upper states via spin orbit coupling.⁴

In the spectrum of the cobalt(II) complex four bands are observed at 8203(s), 10055(sh), 17310(sh) and 21012(s) cm^{-1} which are assigned⁵ to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\gamma_1)$; ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}, {}^2T_{2g}(\gamma_2)$; ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)(\gamma_3)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\gamma_4)$ respectively. The shoulders may arise either due to the splitting of γ_3 in many components or because of the pseudoappearance of γ_2 transition⁶. In the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ for weak field ligands, the term ${}^4T_{1g}(F)$ lies 6 Dq lower and the term ${}^4A_{2g}(F)$ lies 12 Dq higher than the ground term⁷, therefore the band corresponding to this transition is equal to 18 Dq, yielding the value of 10 Dq to be 9610 cm^{-1} and the value of B comes out to be 1001 cm^{-1} . The values of nephelauxetic ratio(β), γ_2/γ_1 and L.F.S.E. in the present Co(II) complex are calculated⁸ as 0.99, 1.92 and 16.45 KCal/mole respectively. The value of β suggests partial covalent character which is also responsible for the reduced magnetic moment of this complex.

The electronic spectra of the present Ni(II) complex consists of three spin-allowed bands due to d-d transitions appearing at 9882 $\text{cm}^{-1}(\gamma_1)$, 16380 $\text{cm}^{-1}(\gamma_2)$, 27025 $\text{cm}^{-1}(\gamma_3)$ and a weak shoulder due to spin-forbidden transition at 12050 $\text{cm}^{-1}(\gamma_4)$ are assigned^{7,9} to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$; ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$; ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^1E_g(D)$ respectively. The values of γ_2/γ_1 , L.F.S.E. in this Ni(II) DIMAGA complex come out to be 1.65, 1024, 0.943 and 34.38 K.Cal/mole respectively, revealing the octahedral symmetry.

A study and comparison of i. r. spectra of the free ligand-DIMAGA and its Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes, reveal the ligand as bidentate with ketonic-oxygen and imine-nitrogen as donor sites.

The sharp absorption bands appearing at 1685 and 1650 cm^{-1} (in free ligand) assigned to $\nu(>C=O)$ and $\nu(-CH=N-)$ respectively show the lowering ($\sim 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in frequencies suggesting $\geq C-O \rightarrow M$ and $-CH=N \rightarrow M$ linkages¹⁰. In the far i. r. spectra of the present complexes, medium intensity bands observed at 320 and 340; 500; 520; 560 and 575 cm^{-1} in Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes respectively are assigned to $\nu(M-Cl)$, $\nu(M-N)$ and $\nu(M-O)$ respectively indicating the different bonds in the complexes.

References

1. R. C. SAXENA, C. L. JAIN and S. C. RASTOGI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 16, 103.
2. R. C. SAXENA, C. L. JAIN and S. C. RASTOGI, *J. Chem. Engg. Data*, 1975, 29, 6.
3. B. N. FIGGIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3138.
4. R. S. NYHOLM, *Proc. Chem. Soc. Aug.*, 1961.
5. L. SACCONI, P. PAOLETTI and M. CIAMPOLINI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 411.
6. A. B. P. LEVER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, A, 2041.
7. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, 'Introduction to Ligand Field Theory' McGraw Hill, N. Y. p. 256, 1962.
8. J. FERGUSON, D. L. WOOD, K. KNOX, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 39, 116 and 887.
9. B. N. FIGGIS, 'Introduction to Ligand Fields' Interscience, N. Y. p. 52, 1962.
10. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETTE and A. CHAKRAVARTY, *Prog Inorg Chem.*, 1966, 7, 161.

Studies on the use of Salicylanilide as a Spectrophotometric Reagent for Uranium (VI)

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THE spectrophotometric determination of uranium (VI) with salicylanilide has been described.

Experimental

Salicylanilide solution : A $4.65 \times 10^{-2} M$ (1%) Solution of recrystallised salicylanilide (BDH) was used.

Uranium (VI) solution : Uranyl nitrate (E-Merck) Solution in dilute nitric acid was standardised¹ and used.

Magnesium-EDTA solution : A 0.01 M solution was prepared from stock magnesium sulphate and $\text{Na}_2\text{-EDTA}$ solutions when required.

Spectrophotometer : A Higher-Watts H700 Uvispek Spectrophotometer with 1-Cm quartz cuvettes was used.

Procedure : Dilute the uranium(VI) (0.15-0.6 mg) solution to 10 ml, heat to 50° on a hot water-bath add 2 ml of the reagent dropwise and adjust the pH to 5.5-7.5 with aqueous pyridine (10%). Cool, transfer into a separatory funnel, wash the container with 5 ml water and extract the complex with 4 ml of isobutyl methol ketone. Separate layers and extract the water-layer twice with 4 ml and 2 ml of the solvent after adding 2 ml and 1 ml of the reagent. Combine the organic layers and dry with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Measure the absorbance within 1 hr at 360 mm against reagent blank.

Add 4 ml of the Mg-EDTA solution before adding the reagent for the first time when foreign metal ions are present.

The procedure is also applicable for uranium ores.

Results and Discussion

The λ_{max} of the uranium(VI)-salicylanilide complex was found to be 360 nm and Beer's law was valid for 1.5-60 mg/ml of the metal ion with the optimum concentration range of 25-45 mg/ml. The Sandell sensitivity was 2.8×10^{-2} mg of uranium (VI) per cm^2 while the molar absorptivity of the complex was $3870.9 \pm 3.06\%$.

The optimum pH range was 5.5 to 7.6 and a minimum of 50 mg of the reagent was required under the conditions of the experiment.